

Policy brief – Deliverable 4.3

Equal opportunities in employment for women and men

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PATHS2INCLUDE

PATHS 2 INCLUDE

European Labour Markets Under Pressure –
New knowledge on pathways to include persons
in vulnerable situations

Title: Equal opportunities in employment for women and men

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PATHS2INCLUDE is a 3-year research project funded by Horizon Europe that investigates the multi-dimensional aspects of discrimination, policies that could reduce inequalities and promote social inclusion in European labour markets and risk factors of vulnerability that may arise in the future of work. The research focuses on three key labour-market processes: recruitment; career paths; and early exit from working life, giving particular attention to labour-market participation at the intersection of gender, ethnicity, age, health, disability, and care responsibilities.

1. Introduction

In all European Union (EU) Member States, a larger percentage of men are employed compared to women (European Commission, 2025). According to the latest EU employment and social developments report (2025), nearly one quarter of women remain outside the labour market. Yet, empowering women and ensuring their full participation across all sectors of the labour market can significantly boost the EU's productivity and economic growth (EIGE, 2025). This persistent gender imbalance highlights the need for a deeper understanding of the barriers that prevent women from fully participating in the labour market.

In March 2025, the EU Roadmap for Women's Rights was adopted, setting out a long-term vision for fully achieving equal opportunities for women in Europe. Moreover, the European Pillar of Social Rights Action Plan aims to increase overall employment in the EU by 2030, including to at least halve the gender employment gap compared to 2019. In addition, with the new Gender Equality Strategy 2026-2030, the European Commission aims to outline concrete measures to be taken to further advance gender equality in Europe.

The PATHS2INCLUDE project sought to obtain a more nuanced understanding of the factors that influence women's labour market inclusion and career trajectories across Europe. Firstly, a part of the research focused on studying the role of social norms and culture in explaining an important part of the gender gap in the labour market. Then, the research explored whether the transition towards more flexible working conditions, as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic, affected the unequal distribution of family responsibilities between men and women and potentially improved gender equality in the labour market. To study these topics, a quantitative approach was used to estimate the causal impact of these factors on women's labour market inclusion and career trajectories across European countries.

Drawing on results of the PATHS2INCLUDE project, this policy brief aims to provide a summary of the most relevant research results as well as policy recommendations that have emerged with the aim to create equal opportunities in employment for women and men. In doing so, the brief seeks to inform and support the upcoming Gender Equality Strategy 2026–2030, contributing to the EU's broader efforts to unlocking the full potential of both women and men in the workforce and to achieve a fair and inclusive labour market for all.

2. Parental gender employment gap

Using data from the European Union – Labour Force Survey (EU-LFS), PATHS2INCLUDE examined how having children affects the labour market situation of parents in Europe (Ayllón & Carralero, 2025). The results show that, in 2023, 79.7% of women aged 25 to 54 without children were employed in the European Union, compared to 74.9% of women with children. The impact of parenthood on men’s employment is the opposite: more men in the same age group with children were employed, compared to men without children. In addition, women, particularly mothers, are much more likely to work on a part-time basis or from home and to experience underemployment than men.

Figure 1. Employment rate by gender and parenthood status, European Union (27), 2009-2023

Note: Adults with and without children aged 25 to 54 in the EU–27.

Source: Own elaboration, using data from the EU-LFS.

This shows a considerable parental gender employment gap, namely that after becoming parents, women’s employment is negatively affected, while men’s employment remains stable or even increases. This is sometimes called the “motherhood penalty” and “fatherhood premium.” In short, parenthood magnifies gender inequality at work and there are still gaps in evidence addressing the causes of these patterns. PATHS2INCLUDE aimed to address these gaps by considering not only the likelihood of being employed, but much broader labour market characteristics and gaps.

3. Barriers and opportunities for gender equal labour markets

This section discusses the main findings of the ‘Factors behind (un)successful labour market inclusion and career trajectories’ research as part of PATHS2INCLUDE, highlighting persisting barriers faced by women when accessing the labour market, while also exploring potential opportunities.

3.1. Persistence of gendered parental roles impacts labour market equality

Although the evolution of gender norms has positively transformed women's labour market positions, traditional views of women as primary caregivers and men as financial providers persist in European societies today. To uncover the causal effects of gender norms, part of the PATHS2INCLUDE research studied not only the extent to which gender norms shape parents' likelihood of being employed, but also the type of job characteristics they hold across 31 European countries, such as remote working, holding multiple jobs, working part-time, etc. (Ayllón & Carralero, 2025).

The findings show that gender norms have more influence on fathers' than mothers' job characteristics. For mothers, more progressive gender norms (measured through levels of religiosity in previous generations, as highly religious societies tend to promote more conservative views about family roles) are associated with higher rates of part-time and remote work. These findings likely indicate that the more non-traditional the region where one lives is, the more likely parents are to take the flexibility that certain jobs allow, possibly with the goal of balancing work and childcare responsibilities. For fathers, however, more progressive gender norms can lead to less part-time work, fewer multiple jobs, and lower rates of underemployed and being in the public sector, and with more often being a supervisor, teleworking or having a high-skilled job, providing them with more advantages in the labour market.

Regional differences were identified, with Nordic countries having more egalitarian gender norms and the smallest employment gaps between mothers and fathers, and Central and Eastern European countries leaning toward more conservative values and higher parental employment gaps. Our study also shows that the gradual move towards more progressive gender norms across Europe is moving slowly and uneven, pointing to the need to tailor policies at the regional level.

Importantly, even within progressive households, the transition to parenthood frequently triggers a reversion to traditional gender roles (Ayllón, 2025). Despite holding non-traditional beliefs, many families continue to experience patterns in which mothers withdraw from the workforce while fathers intensify their professional commitments, indicating that structural and cultural pressure continue to exert greater influence than individual convictions. As a result, women are more often working part-time or in lower-skilled roles, resulting in long-term disadvantages in income, career progression, and retirement. Fathers, on the other hand, may miss out on the emotional and developmental benefits of active caregiving.

These findings indicate that progressive gender norms are not only a positive outcome for women, but for men as well. They enable mothers to benefit from job characteristics that provide them with greater flexibility in the labour market, possibly with the goal of balancing work and childcare responsibilities. For fathers, more progressive gender norms appear to mitigate potential disadvantages in the labour market, such as underemployment, while providing them with certain advantages, including holding a high-skill job.

3.2. Remote work supports labour market inclusion of women

As a result of the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020, remote work has widely expanded across Europe. A causal analysis by Ayllón and Brugarolas (2025), as part of PATHS2INCLUDE research, studied whether the acceleration of remote work helped improve the position of women, particularly mothers, in the labour market. The analysis examined how the flexibility of working from home allows employees to better balance childcare, housework, and their careers. Namely, remote work could provide mothers the possibility to work late once all family duties have been fulfilled, manage working day disruptions and save time from commuting, among other advantages.

The findings show that, overall, the rise in remote work had an overall positive impact on mothers' employment: as remote work increased during the pandemic, so did the likelihood of mothers being employed full-time. This led to a decrease of the employment gap between women with and without children by 25%, in a selection of 20 European countries, since the start of the pandemic (Ayllón and Brugarolas, 2025). Moreover, mothers' working hours also increased in a meaningful way, essentially closing the gap between mothers and childless women's desired working hours. The same is true for actual working hours. Importantly, these findings differ according to the age of the youngest child in the household: the move to full-time work driven by the rise in working from home is strongest among mothers whose youngest child has just started primary school, and, at the same time, mothers with very young children (aged 0 to 2) saw the biggest increase in the number of hours actually worked.

Overall, the results suggest that remote work helps ease time constraints for mothers in two ways: first, by making it easier to move into full-time work when children start primary school (when school days are typically longer and more predictable), and second, by allowing mothers of very young children to increase their working hours. Remote work can support mothers' inclusion in the labour market and reduce the motherhood employment gap, however, its impact varies by children's age and household circumstances, and more is needed to eliminate gender inequalities.

4. Policy recommendations

Based on these research findings, the following recommendations highlight measures which can support reduction of inequalities and promotion of gender equal European labour markets.

These recommendations are relevant for action at national level, as well as at the EU level in the framework of the European Pillar of Social Rights Action Plan, the upcoming EU Gender Equality Strategy, and to support full transposition of the EU Work-Life Balance Directive.

- Support family-friendly workplaces by expanding flexible work arrangements such as remote work, to sustain mothers' employment after childbirth and narrow the motherhood gap.
- Expand access to affordable childcare and promote gender-equal parental leave policies encouraging more equal sharing of care responsibilities between parents.
- Actively challenge gender stereotypes and norms around caregiving and work, by supporting both fathers who choose to be more involved at home and mothers who seek full-time and/or leadership positions.
- Highlight diverse role models in awareness campaigns, media, education, and workplaces to accelerate the normalisation of non-traditional gender roles.
- Encourage employers to adopt measures against discrimination in hiring mothers, including training on diversity management, inclusive hiring practices or mentoring programs.¹
- Tailor policies at the regional level. As cultural attitudes vary significantly between and within countries, tailoring strategies to local values and challenges will be more effective than applying one-size-fits-all solutions.
- Conduct further research into gender norms and employment, the effects of remote work (and all type of flexibility) on other career outcomes (such as wage growth, promotion rates, or job mobility), on mental health and well-being of parents, and into whether differences across skill levels and sectors exist.

¹ See also Buttler (2025) for more recommendations to prevent discrimination in hiring.

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